

A REVIEW OF THE MEASURES OF PERFORMANCE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS AND ITS DETERMINANTS

Shakila Yasmin *
Mohammad Ebadul Islam **

Abstract

Researchers and practitioners have looked beyond conventional profitability ratios to measure performance of commercial banks and thereby presents a plethora of variables to measure performance and its determinants. A clear understanding of these variables and the context of using them are essential for formulating forward looking action plans and strategic insights because commercial banks are considered as the life blood of any economy. As intermediaries, commercial banks facilitate flow of funds from the surplus to deficit units as such to enhance productive activities in the economy. Through a thorough investigation of existing literature on performance analysis of commercial banks this research thrives to build a comprehensive framework to measure bank performance and its determinants. It is evident that besides common profitability ratios, operational and intermediation efficiency and CAMEL model based financial ratios are used to measure bank performance and there are firm specific, industry specific and macro level determinants of performance. To name a few, capital adequacy, asset quality, management efficiency, bank size, sector concentration, GDP growth rate, inflation and others are the key determinants. Practitioners, policy makers and future researchers will find the comprehensive frame work for measuring performance of commercial banks useful for pursuing their respective endeavors.

Keywords : *Commercial Banks, Determinants, Performance Measures.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Commercial banks are the intermediaries to facilitate flow of funds from the surplus to deficit units as such to enhance productive activities in the economy. Smooth functioning of banks is vital for economic growth and development. But different stakeholders often have conflicting expectations from commercial banks. For example, the savers (surplus units) expect high return, safety and liquidity of their savings. On the other hand, borrowers (deficit units) expect quick access to low cost funds. Other customers want commercial banks to provide flawless, quick and versatile payment platform at low cost. To protect the interests of savers, borrowers, and the economy as a whole; regulators come up with various regulations, rules and requirements to control the operation of commercial banks. However, due to conflicting expectations from different stakeholders, commercial banks as well as their regulators constantly juggle in determining appropriate measures of bank performance. During the financial meltdown in 2008 the world has experienced the brink of many bank failures, vulnerabilities of the banking system and their

* Associate Professor, Institute of Business Administration (IBA), University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

** Doctoral Student, DBA Program, Institute of Business Administration (IBA), University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

influence in the overall economies. Therefore, constant monitoring and follow up of bank performance is vital for any economy. But, regular profitability measures of performance portray performance only over particular period of operation and falls short in providing insights on long run performance and effectiveness in meeting the broader objectives of Banks. In order to pin point, the reasons of good or bad performance (in terms of profitability) researchers and practitioners look beyond conventional measures of financial return or profitability. In fact, identification of the appropriate measures of performance is important for building forward looking action plans and strategic insights. Therefore, this research strives to build a comprehensive framework to measure bank performance and its determinants through a thorough investigation of existing literature on performance analysis of commercial banks.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

This paper investigates literature on the performance measures of commercial banks. The objectives of the study are- 1. To identify the different measures of financial/economic performance of commercial banks; and 2. To find out the key determinants of financial/economic performance and their measures.

1.2 Methodology

The study is based on secondary literature review. In order to get a comprehensive view of the literature, cross section of economic/geographic regions and temporal distribution before and after the Financial Crisis of 2008 has been considered. More than 100 published articles were initially reviewed from a high level; based on relevance with the objective of this study 42 of these articles were chosen for in depth analysis. Geographical and temporal distribution of the articles reviewed for this study are presented in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

Table 1: Geographical Distribution of the Articles Analyzed

Geographical Region Covered	No. of Articles
USA	3
Europe	5
USA and Europe together	1
Australia	1
Latin America	3
Middle East	3
Middle East and North Africa together	1
Middle East and Asia together	1
Africa	9
Asia (except Bangladesh)	10
Bangladesh	6
Total	42

Table 2: Temporal Distribution of the Articles Analyzed

Publication Year	No. of Articles	Time horizon covered	No. of Articles
Before 2000	1	Pre-crisis period (2008 financial crisis)	16
2000-2007	4	Post-crisis period	6
2008-2013	22	Pre and Post-crisis period	21
2014- till date	16	Total	42
Total	42		

Descriptive analysis is done in terms of the variables used as the measure of performance, the determinants of performance, the data analysis techniques used and the relationship found between the measures of performance and their determinants.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Literature from the US

Hoffmann and Rodrigo (2011) thrived to identify the determinants of the profitability of commercial banks in the US. They used data over the period 1995-2007. They measured profitability and its inconsistency. Return on equity (ROE) was used as measure of profitability. Using fixed effect, Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimation method they have tested whether and how capitalization, loan ratio, deposit ratio, interest expense, security market exposure, size, goodwill, sector index, sector concentration, industry risk and bank discount rate influence bank profitability. Most of the factors this study has considered are banks specific measures e.g., capitalization, loan ratio, deposit ratio and others whereas others are industry level measures namely sector index, sector concentration and bank discount rate. In this study, capitalization, loan ratio, deposit ratio, size, interest expense and size demonstrate significant negative link with profitability. All other variables considered in the study show significant positive association with profitability except sector index and bank discount rate (relation is statistically insignificant). They also found a significant negative relationship between the size of the bank and its profitability. Thus, a bank can take advantage of the scale of economies at a lower asset size level.

A similar study is conducted by Liu (2013) on the commercial banks of US. But their study emphasized on recent financial crisis. The study tried to determine whether the financial crisis have any impact on bank profitability, its relationship with different bank level, industry level and macro level factors. In fact, this research used the same variables as Hoffman and Rodrigo (2011) study. However, Liu (2013) used data over 2007-2012 period, used return on asset (ROA) as the measure of bank profitability and adopted fixed effect estimation method. Results of the study reveal significant positive association of profitability with capitalization, security market exposure,

bank size and industry risk. Among the other variables used in the study deposit ratio, sector index, sector concentration and bank discount rate assert significant negative influence on bank profitability. The rest of the variables were found to have insignificant impact on profitability. It is eminent that the results of this study deviated to some extent from that of Hoffman and Rodrigo (2011) perhaps due to the financial crisis or due to the use of a different measure of profitability or both. Nevertheless, the researcher did not make any concrete remark on this matter.

Cornett, McNutt and Tehranian (2009) examined the impact of corporate governance on the performance of banks in the United States through Ordinary Least Square (OLS) analysis. They measured performance by earnings after interest and tax. The study reveals that corporate governance as measured by CEO pay-for-performance sensitivity (PPS), board independence, and capital are positively related to earnings. The research therefore suggests corporate governance to be an economic catalyst for the performance of banks.

2.2 Literature from Europe

Based on data from a sample of 645 commercial banks from 13 European countries over the period 1994-98 Staikouras and Wood (2004) thrived to identify the determinants of bank profitability. They measured bank profitability by return on asset and return on equity. Using fixed effect OLS model they affirm that capital ratio, interest rate risk, sector concentration and interest rate (three-month interbank rate) have significant positive influence on profitability and loan ratio, loan loss provision, industry size, interest rate volatility, gross domestic production (GDP) growth, and growth in gross personal income (GPI) have negative impact on profitability. Other variables taken in this study e.g., firm specific market share (MSH) and cost-efficiency did not show any significant association with profitability.

Saeed (2014) studied 73 banks from UK. Based on data over period 2006-2012 the author indentified some micro (bank level), meso (industry level) and macro (country level) factors that influence bank performance. ROA and net interest margin (NIM) were used as the measures of performance in the study. Results of correlation and regression analysis reveal that bank size, loan ratio, capital ratio, liquidity ratio, deposit ratio and market interest rate positively influence profitability. However, GDP growth and inflation rate demonstrate negative impact on bank performance.

Altunbaş and Marqués (2008) examined the impact of European Union banks' strategic similarities on post-merger performance. They measured performance in terms of the common measures of profitability namely ROA, ROE and net profit margin (NPM). The study concluded that contemporary strategies in relation to loan, earnings, cost, deposit and size and credit risk policies are conducive to superior performance. They also inferred that diversity in capital and cost structure has a negative impact on a performance.

Molyneux and Thornton (1992) examined the difference in performance of state owned and private commercial banks across eighteen European countries. They used ROA to

measured bank performance and portray that over the study period (1984-1990) state-owned banks performed significantly better than their private-sector counterparts.

Athanasoglou, Brissimis and Delis (2008) studied commercial banks in Greece and argued that bank performance as measured by NIM is positively affected by management efficiency. They used low credit risk and high capital provision as proxies of management efficiency.

2.3 Literature from US and Europe Together

Hagendorff, Collins and Keasey (2010) gathered data on bank performance from 204 public listed commercial banks from the US and Europe over the period 1996-2004. They used standardized abnormal return (share price based) as the measure of bank performance. With an objective to investigate the role of corporate governance on bank performance they used variables namely board independence, size, board's active involvement, CEO age, tenure and background as the determinants of performance. Based on regression results this study asserts significant negative association of board independence and size and CEO tenure with performance and significant positive association of CEO background, age and boards' active involvement with performance.

2.4 Literature from Australia

Based on 15 years' data (starting from 1999) of commercial banks in Australia Salim, Arjomandi and Seufert (2016) examined whether corporate governance affect bank performance. They used ROA, capital to total asset and loan to total asset ratio as measures of bank performance. Results of data envelopment analysis (DEA) adopted in this study depicted positive influence of corporate governance on bank performance.

2.5 Literature from Latin America

Chortareas, Garza-Garcia and Girardone (2011) explored the indicators of bank performance by analyzing data of 170 commercial banks from 9 Latin American countries over the period 1997-2009. This study used ROA, ROE and NIM as measures of performance. By using data envelopment analysis (DEA) they argued that capital ratio, operational efficiency, managerial cost efficiency, scale efficiency, exchange rate, GDP growth rate, consumer price index (CPI), and average market interest rate are significant factors that explain higher than standard normal performance. They also asserted that market/sector concentration measured by Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) and market share and loan ratio negatively influence bank performance. However, bank size was found to be an insignificant factor of performance.

Figueira, Nellis and Parker (2009) investigated the effect of ownership on bank performance.

They conducted DEA using data of 204 commercial banks from 20 Latin American countries over the period 1997-2008. By using ROA, interest rate spread and net

interest to total asset ratio as the measures of bank performance they asserted that state owned banks perform significantly better than private banks. They argued for considering soundness of capitalization (measured by capital ratio and loan and other loss provisions) and operational efficiency (measured by ratios like, total cost/output, overhead cost/total asset, personnel expense/ total cost, output/total asset and operational income/total asset) as indicators of bank performance.

Jara-Bertin, Moya and Perales (2014) used the data panel system estimator version of GMM on a sample of 78 commercial banks from Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, México, Paraguay, Peru, and Venezuela. By analyzing data over the period of 1995-2010 they ascertain that bank specific factors e.g., service diversification, size, capital ratio, and degree of specialization, and macroeconomic-industrial factors such as economic growth, inflation and sector concentration are the major indicators of bank performance. Their study used common profitability measures e.g., ROA, ROE and NIM as proxy of performance. They also showed that bank performance is negatively related to credit risk, liquidity risk, and operational inefficiencies.

2.6 Literature from Middle East

Bashir (2003) analyzed how bank characteristics and the overall financial environment affect the performance of Islamic banks across eight Middle Eastern countries for the period of 1993-1998. Their study indicates that macroeconomic environment; financial-market structure, taxation rate, capital-to-asset ratio, and loan-to-asset ratios lead to higher profitability. The results also indicated that stock markets and banks are complementary to each other.

Johnes, Izzeldin and Pappas (2008) compared performance of Islamic and conventional banks in GCC (Gulf Cooperation Council) countries by using an efficiency model. They measured cost, revenue and profit efficiency using six financial ratios (two for each) namely cost to income, non-interest expense to total asset, net interest margin, other operating income to total asset, return on asset and return on equity. DEA of five-year data from 2004 to 2007 reveals that that Islamic banks are less cost-effective while more profit and revenue effective as compared to conventional banks. Therefore, the system of banking also has impact on performance.

Through regression analysis, Hassan and Bashir (2003) examined the factors that affect the performance of banks. They utilized cross-country bank-level data on Islamic banks in 21 countries over the period of 1994-2001. They found that the profitability of Islamic banks was positively influenced by high capital and loan-to-asset ratios, favorable macroeconomic conditions.

2.7 Literature from Middle East and North Africa Together

Naceur and Omran (2011) analyzed the banking performance of the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) countries. The empirical results suggested that bank-specific characteristics like capitalization and credit risk have a significant effect on net interest margin, cost efficiency, and profitability. Their study signified that

macroeconomic and financial development indicators have no significant impact on net interest margins, except for economic inflation. Regulatory and institutional variables seem invariably to have an impact on bank performance.

2.8 Literature from Middle and Asia Together

Rosman, Wahab and Zainol (2014) focused on the efficiency level of Islamic banks in Middle Eastern and Asian countries during 2007-2010 through Data Envelopment Analysis technique included 79 Islamic banks across a number of countries. The study found that both profitability and capitalization were the main determinants of Islamic banking efficiency. The findings explained that Islamic banks were able to sustain operations through the crisis.

2.9 Literature from Africa

Ifeacho and Ngalawa (2014) adopted Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) of DEA to investigate and identify the determinants of bank performance using CAMEL (Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Management, Earnings, and Liquidity) model. They used ROA and ROE as the proxy of bank performance. By using data from 4 large banks operating in South Africa over the period 1994-2011 they reveal that asset quality, management quality, and liquidity have a positive effect on both measures of bank performance. This study also found that bank performance is positively related to the interest rate and negatively to unemployment level.

Kumbirai and Webb (2010) investigated the performance of 5 commercial banks from South Africa over the period 2005 - 2009 through the Frequency Response Analysis (FRA) method. They considered profitability, liquidity and asset quality ratios as the measures of bank performance.

Nasserinia, Ariff and Fan-Fah (2017) studied performance of 100 participation banks covering 25 countries in Africa over the financial years 2007-2015. They used profitability ratios ROA and ROE to measure bank performance and found significant strong relationship between performance and five bank-specific variables namely liquidity risk (LR), credit risk (CR), asset quality (AQ), management efficiency (ME) and income diversification (ID). The study did not find any significant influence of nonbank specific factors i.e., GDP growth, inflation and interest rate on bank performance.

Ahokpossi (2013) used interest margin to measure bank performance. Using data from banks in sub-Saharan African countries this study found market concentration, equity, and credit risk to be positively associated with interest margins. The liquidity ratio showed significant negative association with interest margins. Macroeconomic variables such as inflation and GDP growth revealed positive relation with bank performance.

Ally and Patel (2013) investigated performance of 28 commercial banks from Tanzania during the period 2006-2012 using profitability (ROA, ROE, NIM), and liquidity (deposit to total asset) ratios. One year later, Ally (2014) studied the

determinants of bank profitability as measured by ROA, ROE and NIM. Through regression analysis this study identified bank size, capital adequacy, asset quality, expense to asset ratio, liquidity ratio, GDP, inflation and real interest rate as the determinants of bank performance.

Abdallah, Md Amin et al. (2014) used cost and revenue efficiency as the measures of bank performance while analyzing performance of 21 Tanzanian commercial banks over 10-year period starting from 2003. Through stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) they established size and ownership structure to be two significant determinants of performance.

Afolabi, Bosede et al. (2017) studied 5 Nigerian commercial banks over the period 2005-2015 and established that bank performance as measured by earnings per share (EPS), and earnings after tax (EAT) is influenced by bank size, and corporate governance.

A comparative analysis of financial performance of foreign and local commercial banks in Ghana is conducted by Matthew and Laryea (2012). They used CAMEL model to measure bank performance. Equity to total asset, non-performing loan to total asset, interest income to total asset, and advances to deposit ratios were used as proxies of capital adequacy, asset quality, management efficiency and liquidity in this study. ROA, ROE and NIM were taken as proxies of earnings. The results of the study reveal that bank performance is associated with size and type (foreign vs local) of banks.

2.10 Literature from Asia Except Bangladesh

Gardener, Molyneux and Nguyen-Linh's (2011) study on performance of commercial banks stands out in literature because unlike other researchers they used efficiency of intermediation process as the measure of performance. They adopted an input output model where deposits are inputs, interests on deposits and other management costs are expenses and loans, interest income and other revenues are outputs. They used data from banks in five Southeast Asian countries namely Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam and adopted non-parametric data envelopment approach and Tobit regression for data analysis. Their analysis of data over the period 1998–2004 indicates that state-owned banks have greater efficiency than local private banks.

Poon, Yap and Teck-Heang (2013) in their thrive to investigate the influence of politically connected boards on performance of banks used ROE and Tobin's Q as measures of bank performance. Using fixed effect OLS regression analysis of data over period 2000-2009 this study conclude that political connections, tenure, experience and qualifications of the board members influence bank performance.

Sufian (2007) evaluated efficiency of 9 domestic and 7 foreign Islamic banks in Malaysia. The researcher adopted input-output model of intermediation where deposit, labor and total fixed asset were considered as input and total loan and income

(net of expenses) as output. Based on analysis of data over the period 2001-2004 the study asserted that bank profitability (ROA and ROE) has significant positive correlation with efficiency. Five years later, Sufian and Kamarudin (2012) conducted another study to identify the determinants of revenue efficiency of Islamic commercial banks in Malaysia. Their analysis presents five bank-specific determinants namely capitalization, non-traditional activities, liquidity, management quality, and size and three macroeconomic determinants namely GDP growth, inflation, and sector concentration to have significant positive influence on bank performance.

Another study by Sufian (2012) have indentified the determinants of bank performance in developing economies. This research used data over the period 1997-2008 from 77 commercial banks in Srilanka, Pakistan and Bangladesh. Here, common profitability ratios such as ROA, ROE and NIM are used to measure bank performance. Regression analysis results divulge a number of internal (liquidity, size, credit risk, diversification, cost efficiency, and capital adequacy) and external (GDP growth, inflation, private credit, private consumption and equity market size) factors that have significant influence on bank performance.

Baten and Vo (2019) and Le (2017) investigated the factors affecting performance of Vietnamese banks. Both of these studies used common profitability ratios to measure bank performance. Based on DEA, GMM estimation and regression analysis of preceding 10 years' data Baten and Vo (2019) asserted that bank size, credit risk, cost efficiency, capital adequacy, employee productivity, market structure (Herfindahl-Hiroshman Index) and inflation are significant predictors of bank performance. On the other hand, Le (2017) although adopted similar techniques of data analysis identified a different set of variables namely lending specialization, liquidity risk; service diversity, and sector concentration as the determinants of bank performance.

Sinha and Sharma (2016) conducted DEA on data from 42 scheduled commercial banks in India over the period 2000-2013 to identify the determinants of bank performance and its persistency. They used ROA to measure bank performance and the lagged coefficient of autoregressive time series of ROA to measure persistency of performance. Results indicate that besides bank specific factor namely bank size, capital adequacy, credit risk, non-interest income, deposit growth and operational efficiency; several macro factors e.g. sector concentration, GDP growth, inflation have significant influence on performance and its persistency.

Using CAMEL model Sangmi and Nazir (2010) analyzed the financial performance of 2 commercial banks in Punjab and Jammu Kashmir region of India. They used data over 2001-2005 period and presented descriptive statistics of financial ratios such as capital adequacy ratio, non-performing loan ratio, loan loss provision, earnings per employee, credit to deposit ratio, expenditure to income ratio, ROA, ROE, NIM, liquid asset to total asset ratio, liquid asset to deposit ratio and others as proxy of financial performance.

Nisar, Wang et al. (2015) scrutinized the determinants of performance of commercial banks in Pakistan. Based on pooled OLS regression analysis of panel data of 38

scheduled commercial banks over 2006-2013 period they attest that several bank specific factors such as funding cost, liquidity, capital adequacy, administrative expenses, credit risk and non-interest income have significant influence on performance, measured by ROA. Their analysis also indicate that banks perform better during times of economic growth and overall development in the banking sector.

2.11 Literature from Bangladesh

Rayhan, Ahmed and Mondal (2011) conducted a study to evaluate performance and competitiveness of the state owned commercial banks in Bangladesh. They used ROA, ROE, loan losses, profit to expense ratio, net asset value, total assets, EPS, net profit after tax, NPL and others to measure performance.

To analyze bank specific and macro-economic determinants of performance of the commercial banks in Bangladesh Sufian and Kamarudin (2012) used profitability ratios e.g., ROA, ROE and NIM as the proxy of performance. They used data of 31 commercial banks over the period 2000-2010 and conducted regression analysis to identify the determinants of performance. Results indicate that capital adequacy, loan loss ratio (asset quality), liquidity, non-traditional activity, size, GDP growth, Inflation and Sector Concentration are the determinants of bank performance.

Al Karim and Alam (2013) evaluated financial performance of banks using three criterion e.g. internal based criteria ROA, market based criteria Tobin's Q and economic based criteria economic value added (EVA). Based on regression analysis of data from 5 commercial banks over the period 2008-2012 they reveal that bank size, credit risk, operational and asset management efficiency are the significant determinants of performance.

Abdullah, Parvez and Ayreen (2014) conducted correlation analysis to identify bank specific, industry specific and macro factors that determine bank performance. They analyzed 4 year data starting from 2008 of 26 commercial banks listed in security exchange commission of Bangladesh and found that bank size, credit risk, capital adequacy, loan to asset ratio, taxation, cost efficiency, labor productivity, non-traditional activity, sector concentration, sector development and inflation rate are the determinants of performance measured by ROA and NIM.

Rahman, Hamid and Khan (2015) analyzed data from 25 commercial banks in Bangladesh over the period 2006-2013 and identified the determinants of bank performance. They measured bank performance in terms of ROA, ROE, NIM and Tobin's Q. Regression results reveal that capital adequacy, credit risk, liquidity, size, ownership type, non-interest income, non-traditional activity, cost efficiency, GDP growth rate and inflation are significant determinants of bank performance.

Banna, Ahmad and Koh (2017) examined the effect of the global financial crisis and bank specific and macro factors on bank performance. They measured performance in terms of efficiency of intermediation where deposits are considered as input, interest and other expenses are cost and interest revenues, fees and loans as outputs. Based

on the results of DEA and regression analysis of 14-year (2000-2013) time series data from 31 commercial banks in Bangladesh they asserted that bank size, ROE, capital adequacy and real interest rate have significant influence on bank performance. They did not find any significant association of bank performance with ownership type, financial crisis and inflation rate.

3. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

3.1 Measures of Performance

From the analysis of literature presented above it can be asserted that diverse measures of performance used by the researchers can be classified into three major categories e.g., profitability measures, efficiency-based measures, CAMEL model-based measures. Profitability ratios are most widely (74%) used measure of performance followed by efficiency-based (19%) and CAMEL model-based (7%) measures. Some of the articles reviewed for this study have used combination of the above three types of measures (12%). Apart from the above three categories few researchers used several internal, market and economy-based and other measures (14%). Table 3 presents the measures of performance and their prevalence observed in literature reviewed for this paper.

Table 3: Prevalence of Different Measures of Performance

Type of Measure	Prevalence (count)	Prevalence (%)
Profitability Measures	31	74%
Efficiency-based Measures	8	19%
CAMEL Model-based Measures	3	7%
Other measures	6	14%
Total	47	114%

*Total is more than the number of articles reviewed for this study (above 100%) because some of the researches use combination of different types of measures.

3.1.1 Profitability Measures

Among the measures of profitability, ROA and ROE are most common. Other measures of profitability found to be used by the researchers include NIM, EPS and NPM. Rather than the ratios stated above, few of the studies analyzed for this study have used absolute measure of profitability namely earnings after tax (EAT).

Table 4 presents a list of the measures of profitability used, their prevalence and the formulae to calculate them. All the profitability measures identified here are common and widely used to evaluate corporate performance except NIM. This is a measure unique for businesses involved in collection of deposits and lending activities. Banks and most nonbank financial institutions fall in this category of business.

Table 4: Prevalence of the Measures of Profitability and Formulae to Calculate them

Measure of Profitability	Prevalence (count)	Prevalence (%)	Formulae
Return on Asset (ROA)	29	69%	$\frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Total Assets}}$
Return on Equity (ROE)	22	52%	$\frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Total Equity}}$
Net Interest Margin (NIM)	17	40%	$\frac{\text{Net Interest Income}}{\text{Total Asset}}$
Earnings per Share (EPS)	2	5%	$\frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{No of Shares Outstanding}}$
Net Profit Margin (NPM)	1	2.5%	$\frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Total Revenue}}$
Earnings After Tax (EAT)	3	7%	$(\text{Revenue}-\text{Expenses})^*$ $(1-\text{Tax rate})$

*Total count in Table 4 is higher than the count of profitability ratio in Table 3 because many studies used multiple measures.

3.1.2 Efficiency-based Measures

Efficiency-based approach to measure performance follows input-output model. Efficiency is measured by output as percentage of input. This approach has two main streams. The first stream focuses on operational efficiency where cost, revenue and profit efficiencies are measured separately. The essence of the second stream is efficiency of intermediation where deposits and total fixed assets are considered as input; interest on deposit, management and other costs are expense and loans, interest income and other revenues are treated as outputs.

3.1.2.1 Operational Efficiency

Operational efficiency approach is applicable to all forms of business, whereas the intermediation efficiency approach is applied specifically to businesses involved in providing intermediary services. Out of 8 studies which adopted efficiency-based approach 3 used intermediation efficiency and the rest used operational efficiency. Table 5 presents the formulae used to measure cost, revenue and profit components of operational efficiency.

Table 5: Measures of Operational Efficiency

Measures of Operational Efficiency	Formulae
Cost Efficiency	$\text{Cost to Income} = \frac{\text{Overhead expenses}}{\text{Net Interest revenue} + \text{other income}}$ $\text{Expense to Asset} = \frac{\text{Overhead expenses}}{\text{Total Asset}}$ $\text{Non-interest expense to Asset} = \frac{\text{Overhead expenses} + \text{loan loss provision}}{\text{Total Asset}}$
Revenue Efficiency	$\text{Net Interest Margin} = \frac{\text{Net interest revenue}}{\text{Total Asset}}$ $\text{Other Income to Asset} = \frac{\text{Other operating income}}{\text{Total Asset}}$
Profit Efficiency	$\text{ROA} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Asset}} ; \text{ ROE} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Equity}}$
Overall Operational Efficiency	$\text{Operating expense to Asset} = \frac{\text{Total operating expenses}}{\text{Total Asset}}$ $\text{Operating expense to Interest} = \frac{\text{Total operating expenses}}{\text{Net Interest Revenue}}$

A close scrutiny of the ratios used by the researchers to measure operational efficiency reveals that profit efficiency and one measure of revenue efficiency i.e., NIM actually represents profitability ratios broadly used by most other researchers. However, other measures expand the horizon of performance. For example, cost to income ratio indicates the effectiveness of overhead expenses in generating income. Higher the ratio lower is the effectiveness or utilization of overhead expenses to convert it into revenue. Similarly, operating expense to interest ratio determines to what extent operating expenses are converted into net interest revenue. Lower value indicates higher efficiency and better performance. Another variance of operational efficiency model is production efficiency where banks are considered to be producer of services for its customers. Thereby, production efficiency is measured by the number of transactions and/or number of deposit accounts opened per employee; loan document processed per employee; deposit to total expense ratio; income to expense ratio and others. However, production efficiency model is suitable for evaluating performance of bank branches who have little control over equity and overall business strategies (Sufian, 2007)

3.1.2.2 Intermediation Efficiency

The proponents of intermediation efficiency view banks as intermediary between savers and borrowers. As mentioned earlier they consider deposits and physical capital assets as inputs; labor, management and other costs as expenses and loans, interest and other revenues as output. Hence, financial ratios that can be used to measure intermediation efficiency may comprise loan to deposit ratio, net income to deposit ratio, loan to deposit plus capital asset ratio, net interest income to deposit plus capital asset ratio and others. But the problem with using financial ratios to measure efficiency is that they measure efficiency in terms of one particular input

and output at a time. Even when different outputs and inputs are aggregated together simple ratios fail to capture the effect of interactions among the variables. Perhaps, to address this issue researchers have historically used different statistical tools such as stochastic frontier analysis (SFA), technical inefficiency effect model (TIEM), DEA and others to determine intermediation efficiency of banks (Gardener, Molyneux and Nguyen-Linh, 2011). All these statistical techniques measure efficiency in relation to a multivariate optimum model of efficiency where weighted average output is maximized with given levels of weighted average inputs under a number of constraints; in other words, for a given level of output, input is minimized.

The three papers adopting intermediation approach, as found from the literature survey of this research, used DEA. DEA is run with given time series values of input and output variables to get time series value of efficiency. The underlying mathematical model to measure efficiency in DEA is as follows-

$$\text{Min } \lambda_0 \theta_0$$

Subject to,

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_{0j} y_{rj} \geq y_{r0} \quad r = 1, 2, 3, \dots, s$$

$$\theta_0 x_{i0} \geq \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_{0j} x_{ij} \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_{0j} \neq 1$$

$$\lambda_{0j} \geq 0 \quad j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$$

Where, θ_0 is the measure of efficiency, λ is weight of the input and output variables, x represent input variable and y represent output variable and j represent the number of bank.

The result of DEA using the above model provides overall banking efficiency often named as technical efficiency (TE). In order to have a more elaborated view of performance researchers have broken it into other forms of efficiency. For example, Sufian (2007) has dissected technical efficiency into scale efficiency and pure technical efficiency. Scale efficiency (SE) measures the ability of management to deploy optimum size of resources. By demonstrating whether a particular intermediary or unit has constant return to scale, increase return to scale or decreasing return to scale, SE identifies if there is any inefficiencies in terms of determining the optimum size. Oversized businesses will result in decreasing return to scale and undersized businesses will result in increasing return to scale. Pure technical efficiency (PTE) determines the managerial performance to effectively organizing the given level of resources to have best possible outcome. The mathematical model behind PTE is presented below-

$$\text{Min } \lambda_0 \theta_0$$

Subject to,

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_{0j} y_{rj} \geq y_{r0} \quad r = 1, 2, 3, \dots, s$$

$$\theta_0 x_{i0} \geq \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_{0j} x_{ij} \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_{0j} = 1$$

$$\lambda_{0j} \geq 0 \quad j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$$

$$\text{SE} = \text{TE}/\text{PTE}$$

Gardener, Molyneux and Nguyen-Linh (2011) divided TE into allocative efficiency (AE) and cost efficiency (CE). An organization is more cost efficient (CE) if it can deliver same level of output by using same level of inputs as other organizations but with lower cost. In this case, labor, overhead, management and other expenses are considered separately from inputs e.g., deposit and capital assets. On the other hand, allocative efficiency (AE) reveals a firm's ability to opt for the mix of inputs that can be used to deliver a given level of output at lowest possible cost. Cost-minimization efficiency requires solution of the following mathematical model-

$$\text{Min } w_j x_{j0}^*$$

Subject to,

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j y_{rj} \geq y_{rj0} \quad r = 1, 2, 3, \dots, s$$

$$x_{j0}^* \geq \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j x_{ij} \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j = 1$$

$$\lambda_j \geq 0 \quad j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$$

Where, w_j is the input price vector and x_j^* is the cost minimization vector of the input quantities. Cost efficiency (CE) is the ratio of minimum cost to observed cost as presented in the equation below-

$$\text{CE} = \frac{w_j x_{j0}^*}{w_j x_{j0}}$$

Allocative efficiency (AE) is calculated by dividing cost efficiency (CE) by technical efficiency (TE)

$$\text{AE} = \text{CE}/\text{TE}$$

3.1.3 CAMEL Model Based Measures

CAMEL stands for Capital, Asset, Management, Earnings and Liquidity. Researches adopting this model can be divided into two groups. One group considers earnings as the measure of performance and other dimensions (or variables) of CAMEL as the determinants of bank performance. Whereas, the other group considers all five dimensions (or variables) of CAMEL as the measures of performance. Among the three studies that used CAMEL model as identified in the literature review section of this paper; two namely Matthew and Laryea (2012) and Ifeacho and Ngalawa (2014) fall in the first group and the other one by Sangmi and Nazir (2010) falls in second group. Apart from the above variation in the use of CAMEL model; empirical studies have used different financial ratios to measure the underlying variables. Table 6 presents these financial ratios found from the literature reviewed for this study.

Some researchers although did not adopt CAMEL model, used some of the variables in CAMEL besides common profitability ratios to measure bank performance. For example, Salim, Arjomand and Seufert (2016) used capital adequacy and liquidity ratios besides profitability. Likewise, Kumbirai and Webb (2010) used asset quality and liquidity ratios and Naceur and Omran (2011) used capital adequacy and asset quality ratios along with profitability.

Table 6: Financial Ratios Used to Measure CAMEL Variables

Variable	Financial Ratio
Capital	$\text{Capital Adequacy} = \frac{\text{Total Equity}}{\text{Total Asset}};$ $\text{Leverage Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total loan}}{\text{Total Asset}};$ $\text{Capital Strength} = \frac{\text{Tier 1 and 2 capital} + \text{loan loss provisions} - \text{non performing loan}}{\text{Total asset}};$ $\text{Net-worth protection} = \frac{\text{Net worth}}{\text{Non performing asset}}$
Asset	$\text{Asset Quality} = \frac{\text{Nonperforming loan}}{\text{Total loans and advances}};$ $\text{Bank Size} = \text{Total Asset};$ $\text{Asset Quality} = \frac{\text{Total Asset}}{\text{Capital employed}};$ $\text{Credit deposit ratio} = \frac{\text{Total credit}}{\text{Total deposit}}$
Management	$\text{Management efficiency} = \frac{\text{Interest income}}{\text{Total Asset}};$ $\text{Management efficiency} = \frac{\text{Operating Income}}{\text{No. of employees}};$ $\text{Expenditure income ratio} = \frac{\text{Total expenditure}}{\text{Total income}}$ $\text{Expenditure per employee} = \frac{\text{Total expenditure}}{\text{No of employees}}$
Earnings	$\text{ROA} = \frac{\text{Net profit}}{\text{Total Asset}}; \text{ROE} = \frac{\text{Net profit}}{\text{Total Equity}};$ $\text{NIM} = \frac{\text{Net interest Income}}{\text{Total asset}}$
Liquidity	$\text{Loan to Deposit} = \frac{\text{Total loans and advances}}{\text{Total Deposit}};$ $\text{Current Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current asset}}{\text{Current Liability}};$ $\text{Liquid asset to total asset} = \frac{\text{Liquid asset}}{\text{Total asset}};$ $\text{Government other security to total asset} = \frac{\text{Government other securities}}{\text{Total asset}};$ $\text{Liquid asset to deposit} = \frac{\text{Liquid asset}}{\text{Deposit}};$ $\text{Investment to deposit} = \frac{\text{Investment}}{\text{Deposit}}$

3.1.4 Other Measures of Performance

Apart from the measures of profitability, efficiency and CAMEL-based variables presented before number of other measures have been used by researchers who have done empirical studies to investigate bank performance. For example, Hagendorff, Collins and Keasay (2010); Al Karim and Alam (2013); Poon, Yap and Teck-Heang (2013) and Rahman, Hamid and Khan (2015) used market-based or share price-based measure of performance. Later three used Tobin's Q (the ratio of market value to book value of the bank). Market value is calculated by multiplying the number of outstanding shares with prevailing market price per share. Book value is the balance sheet value of the assets of the bank. In an efficient market, share price is likely to reflect prospective performance of a company. Therefore, high or increasing value of Tobin's Q represent good or rising prospect of performance. Hagendorff, Collins and Keasay (2010) used Standardized Abnormal Return (SAR), a comparatively complicated share price-based measure of performance. Abnormal return (AR) is an extra ordinary return that is triggered by certain events such as merger, acquisitions, earning and other announcements etc. which have not been priced by the market yet. As abnormal return is likely to be highly volatile and the volatility vary across firms as well as events; to get a comparable measure of abnormal return SAR is calculated by dividing excess abnormal return relative to a matching return of a controlled entity divided by standard deviation of abnormal return. The formula used to calculate SAR is presented here-

$$SAR = \frac{AR}{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\delta\sqrt{T} + \frac{1}{T_i} + \frac{(R_{mt} - R_m)^2}{\Sigma(R_{mt} - R_m)^2} \right)}$$

where:

δ = estimation period variance of AR

T = number of days (100) in the estimation period

R_{mt} = return of the concerned bank

R_m = average return on the market index

Considering the fact that profitability or performance over a particular period is unlikely to remain constant; Hoffman and Rodrigo (2011) used profitability ratio and its dispersion over time as the measure of performance. Correspondingly, Sinha and Sharma (2016) did not rely on average or periodical measures of profitability ratios. They argued that profitability of a particular period is just a snap shot of performance whereas historical average is the expected performance. Hence, they thrived to measure persistence performance. They determined the lagged coefficient of autoregressive time series of profitability ratio i.e., ROA. Greater than 1 value or large value of the coefficient represents persistent performance.

Some other researchers used several accounting measures such as loan loss provision, net asset value, interest rate spread, profit to expense ratio, total asset value, economic

value added and others besides common profitability ratios. For instance, Al Karim and Alam (2013) used economic value added (EVA = after tax operating profit – total capital * cost of capital) as an economy based measure of performance; Figueria, Nellis and Parker (2009) used interest rate spread (the difference between average lending and borrowing rate); Rayhan, Ahmed and Mondal (2011) supplemented common profitability ratios with measures like nonperforming loan (NPL), NPL ratio, loan loss provision, profit to expense ratio, net asset value, growth of branches, growth in number of employees, growth in deposit and others.

3.2 Determinants of Performance

The determinants of performance can be divided in three categories e.g., i) firm or bank specific factors, ii) industry specific factors and iii) economy wide factors. Most of the literature reviewed for this study have considered factors from all three category; however, some of them did not focus on identifying the determinants while others tested relationship performance with one or two particular determinants. Table 7 shows the number of studies using one or more categories of determinants.

Table 7: Categories of Determinants and their Use

No. of Studies	% of Studies	Categories of Determinants Used
12	28%	Firm and industry specific and macro variables
4	9%	None
13	30%	Only firm specific
9	21%	Firm specific and macro variables
4	9%	Firm and industry specific factors
1	2%	Only macro variables

Studies that did not shed light on any determinants of performance presented only the descriptive analysis of performance and touched upon how performance changed over time.

3.2.1 Firm Specific Determinants

The firm specific factors used in literature include capital, asset, management and liquidity variables of CAMEL model but not limited to those. Firm specific determinants also involve many other variables such as Interest expense, security market exposure, bank size, goodwill, market share, credit risk, operational, cost and scale efficiency, non-traditional activities, service diversity, degree of specialization, ownership type, strategies related to size, credit risk, loan, deposit and earnings, corporate governance, political connections of board members and others.

Table 8: Prevalence of Firm Specific Determinants in Literature and their Expected Impact on Performance

Name of the Determinant	Prevalence in Literature	Impact on Performance
Capital Adequacy	Very High	Positive
Asset Quality	Very High	Positive
Management Efficiency	High	Positive
Liquidity	Very High	Positive
Size	Very High	Positive
Credit Risk	Very High	Negative
Security Market Exposure	Low	Negative
Interest Expense	Low	Negative
Good will	Low	Positive
Cost efficiency	Moderate	Positive
Operational efficiency	Moderate	Positive
Scale efficiency	Low	Positive
Non-traditional activity	Moderate	Positive
Service diversification	Moderate	Positive
Degree of specialization	Low	Positive
Market share	Low	Positive
Corporate governance	Moderate	Positive
Bank type		
Private vs public	Moderate	Public perform better
Foreign vs local		Foreign perform better
Islamic vs conventional		Islamic perform better
Strategy (aggressive, moderate, defensive)	Low	Depends on other factors

3.2.2 Industry Specific Determinants

The industry specific determinants of performance as found from the literature review of this study comprise of sector index, sector concentration, and size, structure, development and risk of the industry. Well structured, developed and large industry sector facilitate good performance of the banks operating in the industry. But industry risk and sector concentration and sector index exert negative stimulus on performance. Sector concentration is found to be most widely used industry specific determinant of performance followed by industry structure and development. Prevalence of the others is low in literature. Industry risk, structure and development are measured by several subjective measures such as regulations, competition, over

all technological back bone, availability of skilled manpower, aggregate growth of the sector and others. Both sector concentration and sector index as measured by the following formulae represent the level of competition in the industry sector. High value indicates monopolistic market meaning that few companies are dominating the industry and eating up lion share of market.

$$\text{Sector Concentration} = \frac{\text{Total asset of 3 or 5 largest bank}}{\text{Total Asset of all banks}}$$

$$\text{Herfindahl-Hirschman Index(HHI)} = \sum (\text{Market share of each bank})^2$$

3.2.3 Macro Economic Determinants

GDP growth rate and inflation are the most widely used macro level determinants of bank performance followed by market interest rate, volatility in interest rate, and structure and development of financial markets in the economy. Growth in personal income depicts moderate prevalence in literature as one of the macro-economic determinants of bank performance. Other macro variable such as unemployment rate, consumer price index, exchange rate, taxation rate show low prevalence. Macro variables that indicate overall economic development such as GDP growth, inflation, growth in personal income and consumer price index and development of financial markets are likely to portray positive impact on bank performance; whereas, increase in interest rate and its volatility, taxation rate, and unemployment rate are expected to negatively influence bank performance.

3.3 Data Analysis Techniques Used

Given the time series nature of data collected from multiple banks, most of the studies covered under literature review of this paper deployed statistical techniques applicable for panel data. Simple correlation analysis, regression analysis and data envelopment analysis are the top most common techniques used by the researchers focusing of bank performance and its determinants. Most studies using regression analysis have used fixed effect ordinary least square model. Table 9 presents the incidence of data analysis techniques used by the researches reviewed for this study.

Table 9: Incidence of Different Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis technique	Incidence
Correlation and Regression analysis	Very high
Data envelopment analysis	Very high
Generalized method of moments	High
Independent sample t-test	Moderate
General descriptive statistics	Moderate
Stochastic frontier analysis, Frequency response analysis, Tobit regression and others	Low

Good number of studies whose data set had semi-parametric variables have used GMM. Studies investigating the impact of one particular determinant on bank performance such as Molyneux and Thornton (1992); Athanasoglou et al. (2008) and Matthew and Laryea (2012) used independent sample t-test. Only one of them namely Aluntbas and Marques (2008) used analysis of variance (ANOVA). Other studies such as Sangmi and Nazir (2010); and Rayhan, Ahmed and Mondal (2011) which analyzed performance over time and did not investigate any factors influencing performance used common descriptive statistics such as mean, median, mode, trend etc. A few studies e.g., Kumbirai and Webb (2010); Abdullah, Md Amin et al. (2014) and Gardener, Molyneux and Nguyen-Linh (2011) respectively used other techniques such as FRA, SFA and Tobit Regression Model. Some of the studies used a combination of statistical analysis techniques in order to fulfill different stated objectives. For example, Gardener, Molyneux and Nguyen-Linh (2011) used DEA and Tobit Regression analysis; Banna, Ahmad and Koh (2017) used DEA and multiple regression analysis; Baten and Vo (2019) used DEA, GMM and regression analysis and Liu (2013) used regression analysis and independent sample t-test; to name few.

4. CONCLUSION

This study has investigated literature relating to bank performance measures and their determinants. Analysis of literature indicates that besides common profitability ratios many other measures namely efficiency-based measures and CAMEL model-based measures of performance has been used by the researchers. Efficiency-based measures, especially that focus on intermediation efficiency, are less prevalent than profitability ratios. Perhaps the complex mathematical model required to measure intermediation efficiency has been responsible for its lower prevalence. CAMEL model although simple and base mainly on financial ratios, most researchers adopting this model considered the factor earnings as the measure of performance. They then investigated the influence of the other factors in the model e.g. capital, asset, management and liquidity on earnings. Earnings are measured using common profitability ratios. Hence the prevalence of CAMEL model as the measure of performance was found to be limited. In terms of the determinants of performance, literature suggests three categories of determinants i.e., firm specific, industry specific and macro-economic factors. Capital adequacy, asset quality, liquidity, operating and management efficiency are found to be the most common firm specific determinants of performance; henceforth coincides with the CAMEL model of bank performance. Size, type of bank, and corporate governance are other major firm specific determinants. Sector concentration is the most prominent industry specific determinant and GDP growth rate, inflation and interest rate are found to be the most pervasive macro level determinant of performance. This paper also summarized the data analysis techniques used in literature. Regression analysis and DEA were found to be the most widely used techniques adopted by the researchers. Other statistical techniques used include GMM, correlation analysis, independent sample t-test, ANOVA, FRA, SFA and others.

This study contributes to the literature by providing a summarized framework for performance analysis of Banks. The framework derived in this research is likely to provide guidelines for variable identification, measurement and data analysis techniques to be deployed by future researchers, practitioners and policy makers focusing on bank performance analysis. Policy makers and practicing managers may also use this framework to identify key determinants of performance and thereby formulate policies and strategies to bring positive changes by influencing those determinants. The performance measurement framework derived in this research can also be adopted for non-financial business organizations, not to mention nonbank financial institutions.

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